

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

PRODUCTIVITY OF MAIZE HYBRIDS IN POLISSIA AND FOREST-STEPPE OF UKRAINE

Stoliar S.,

*Head of the Department of Technology in Crop Production,
Candidate of Agricultural Sciences, Associate Professor*

Trembitska O.,

Candidate of Agricultural Sciences,

Associate Professor of the Department of Soil Science and Agriculture

Petrenko N.,

Kaftanatii D.,

Sagan R.

applicants for master's degree

Polissia National University

Zhytomyr, Ukraine

ABSTRACT

The article presents the results of research on the productivity of grain and sugar corn hybrids in the Polissia and Forest-Steppe regions of Ukraine. The yield, grain quality and resistance to environmental stress factors of the hybrids were evaluated. It was found that the agroclimatic conditions of these regions significantly affect the productivity of the crop, in particular, its ability to form a stable grain yield and increase the sugar content in the cobs of sugar corn. The onset of phenological phases of development and their influence on yield indicators were studied. The results are useful for improving corn growing technologies and selecting the most productive hybrids for different climatic zones of Ukraine.

Keywords: corn for grain, sugar corn, yield, grain quality.

Corn production is an important component of Ukraine's grain sector. It is a unique raw material for the feed, food, medical, microbiological and processing industries. In addition, corn grain is a high-energy raw material for industrial bioethanol production [1, 2].

Corn grain is characterized by high feed value – 1 kg contains 1.3 feed units, 1 kg of silage contains 0.28–0.32 feed units and 14–18 g of digestible protein. The grain contains about 65–70 % of nitrogen-free extractives, 9–12 % of protein, 4–5 % of fat, and very little fiber [3, 4, 5].

Corn is an important food product. The grain is used to make flour, cereals, oil, canned food, starch, syrup, alcohol, sugar, and beer. The processing industry produces liquid resin, butyl alcohol, furfural, insulating pads, glue, and medicines from the leaf and stem mass [6, 7, 8].

Zea mays plays a significant agrotechnical role. An important agricultural measure that has a positive impact on the level of yield is the introduction of new high-yielding hybrids into production (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Agricultural price of corn: a – for grain, b – for sugar, 2023–2024

The number of hybrids listed in the Register of Varieties of Ukraine is constantly changing, with more productive ones with improved economically valuable traits. The newly developed hybrids differ in productivity, morphology, early maturity, resistance to pests and lodging, response to technological methods and moisture conditions, ability to accelerate moisture release by grain, and heat resistance. Technological experience in

maize cultivation shows that it is worth choosing the right hybrid for certain management conditions, and not the maturity group, as it was before [9, 10].

Therefore, the aim of our experiments was to determine the yield and quality of grain and sugar corn hybrids in Polissia and Forest-Steppe regions of Ukraine.

Research methodology. Field research on the yield and quality of grain and sugar corn hybrids was conducted in the conditions of the Niva – PE farm in Berdychiv district and the Ukraine farm in Zhytomyr district, Zhytomyr region during 2023–2024. Laboratory studies were conducted at the departments of plant production technologies, soil science and agriculture, as well as in a certified laboratory of Polissia University.

It should be noted that during the field experiment, air temperature and precipitation significantly differed from the long-term average, which provided different conditions for corn growing, and, accordingly, reliable data

The air temperature in April 2023 was moderate, ranging from 7 °C to 15 °C, not exceeding the long-term average. However, the amount of precipitation increased twice as much as normal and amounted to 100 mm of precipitation. However, in May, there was a precipitation deficit (0.2 mm) and a rapid increase in air temperature to +17.7 °C.

Summer began with average temperatures ranging from 17 °C to 25 °C. Precipitation was highest in July, when it amounted to about 78 mm. This provided sufficient moisture, but also increased the risk of crop diseases due to wet conditions.

Air temperatures in August were 4.8 °C above the long-term average. Precipitation was in short supply, falling 70 % below the long-term average.

The beginning of autumn brought a drop in temperatures ranging from 14 °C to 22 °C. The amount of precipitation was within 30 mm, which generally contributed to the final stage of ripening and harvesting.

The weather conditions in 2024 from April to August reflected a typical transition from spring to summer, with a variety of climatic conditions affecting agricultural activities.

April was relatively warm, with an average temperature of about 12.2 °C, which is 1.4°C above the long-term average. The minimum temperature dropped to 10.5 °C, and the maximum temperature reached about 14.4 °C. In April, there was double the amount of precipitation, totaling about 100 mm. This precipitation was distributed throughout the month, providing the necessary moisture for early spring crops and contributing to the gradual warming of the soil. In May, the average temperature was 15.5°C, which was crucial for germination and early growth of many crops. However, precipitation was half the normal level of 17.7 mm.

June marked the beginning of summer, with average temperatures reaching 20.7 °C, which contributed to the rapid growth of spring crops. In June, there was a significant amount of precipitation – about 72 mm, which provided the necessary amount of moisture for the growth and development of corn plants. July was the warmest month with an average temperature of 23.6 °C, which was 1.4 °C above normal. Precipitation was within the normal range of 29.4 mm. In August, temperatures began to drop slightly, averaging 20.9 °C. The minimum temperature was around 14 °C and the maximum temperature was around 23.1 °C, indicating a slow transition to autumn. Precipitation was around 23 mm, which is less than in July, but still enough to

support late spring crops and preserve soil moisture. September was cool, with temperatures around 13 °C and dry.

Overall, the weather conditions during the study period were characterized by a gradual increase in temperature from April to July, with July being the hottest and wettest month. The high rainfall in July provided the necessary moisture for agriculture, but also created problems such as delays in harvesting. These meteorological conditions were generally favorable for crop growth and development, although high humidity and precipitation in the summer months may have required careful management to prevent disease and pest spread.

Understanding these climatic patterns is crucial for planning agricultural activities, from sowing to harvesting, and ensuring the sustainability of food production in the region. To summarize, the weather conditions during 2023–2024 were favorable for corn growing.

Results. To increase corn yields, it is important to select hybrids for a given zone and a particular farm. The potential reserves of hybrids are not equal. Therefore, their proper selection according to the direction of use and plant biology allows to increase the production of seeds and fodder without unnecessary labor and money.

The purpose of our research is to study the growth characteristics and formation of economically important traits of individual yield of maize hybrids in the soil and climatic conditions of a particular farm.

The development of maize is conditioned by certain phases: germination, inflorescence, flowering of inflorescences, appearance of tassels, and grain ripening (milky, waxy, and full). In order for the grains to germinate, certain conditions must be created: temperature, humidity, and oxygen access.

During the germination phase, the grain swells and absorbs water (50 % of dry weight). First, the root of the germ develops. It breaks the root sheath and goes deeper into the soil. A sprouted corn seed has a single root. Later, a bud develops. It has a growth point and green leaves covered with a modified leaf (coleoptile). The coleoptile has a strong turgor, and green leaves, rolled into a tube, appear through the soil. The leaf first forms the top and then the base.

Observations of the developmental phases of corn hybrids during sowing in 2023 showed that seedlings appeared simultaneously (May 12). The total number of leaves formed by corn is a sign of early maturity. Fewer leaves (10–11) are formed by early-ripening varieties and hybrids, and more (up to 20) by late-ripening varieties. With the formation of the 3rd leaf, the appearance of each (5, 7, 9) subsequent unpaired leaf is noted. A sign of the phase is the appearance of the top of the leaf blade from the leaf sheath. The emergence of the third leaf in the experimental variants took place on 30.05–1.06. First in hybrids DKS 4014, Adeway, and two days later in hybrids NK Lemoro and DN Patriot. The appearance of 7–9 leaves also occurred at different calendar dates. Thus, in the hybrid Adeway – 18.06, DCS 4014 - 19.06, NC Lemoro and DN Patriot – 20.06.

Panicle ejection completes the formation of maize leaves. It is recognized by the appearance of the upper

lobe of the panicle from the sheath of the last leaf. The phase of panicle ejection occurs on 10.07–11.07. In the first, third and fourth variants – on July 11, and in the Adeway hybrid – on July 10.

The flowering of the panicle is noted with the appearance of anthers on the main inflorescence filament. At waxy ripeness, the grain acquires the color characteristic of the variety. Its consistency is similar to wax, the grain is simply cut with a knife, but no liquid is released under these conditions. The dried wrapper loses its green color. The beginning of flowering of cobs in

Adeway hybrids occurred on 20.07, DCS 4014, NC Lemoro and DN Patriot – on 21.07.

Milk ripeness occurred on 07.08–09.08. First in the Adeway hybrid (7.08), and then in the control variant, where the corn hybrid was grown. The onset of milky-wax ripeness occurred on 24.08 in the hybrid Adeway and DCS 4014, on 25.08 in the hybrid NK Lemoro, on 26.08 in the variant DN Patriot.

The wax ripeness of seeds in the experimental plots was noted on 19.09–20.09 (Fig. 2).

DKS 4014

Adeway

NC Lemoro

DN Patriot

Fig. 2. Corn hybrids for grain, 2023

Long-term observations confirm that the yield of different corn biotypes varies greatly over the years and depends mainly on the weather during the growing season: soil moisture regime, air temperature, frequency of droughts, etc., as well as on the biopotential of the hybrid.

The degree of yield and, most importantly, seed moisture content is also closely related to production losses required for all technological operations of growing, harvesting and post-harvest processing. Early maturing hybrids have less crude grain that requires low post-harvest processing costs, which determines the level of profitability. In other words, the technology of growing hybrids of the early maturing group is the most profitable in terms of payback for the entire cycle of work.

The analysis of the results of the introduction of new corn hybrids with increased grain productivity and accelerated moisture return by grain shows a significant increase in yield and improvement of economic efficiency of production. The current model of hybrid composition can ensure an increase in grain yield by more than 1.2 tons per hectare with appropriate technology elements. This is primarily due to the introduction of

early and mid-early hybrids that have increased heat and drought resistance during the harvesting period.

Today's farming practices are increasingly focused on agronomic measures aimed at increasing crop yields. The transition to them is inseparable from the production of the cheapest products. A pressing problem in today's agricultural production is the development of technologies that increase yields while being environmentally friendly and healthy for the environment and human health. Corn is one of the leading grain and fodder crops. Expanding its cultivation and increasing its yield is an important reserve for increasing gross grain harvests and producing high-quality fodder.

An important task for the Ukrainian agro-industrial complex in the current socio-economic environment is to ensure significant growth and stability of food corn seed production. The so-called limits of adaptation or endurance are defined for various environmental factors for each variety or hybrid. Therefore, the study of seed yield in the conditions of the farm "Niva – PP" is relevant.

From the data of Fig. 3 shows that the yields of the hybrids were not the same.

Fig. 3. Yields of corn hybrids for grain, 2022–2024

The maximum grain yield in all years of the study was formed by the Adeway hybrid, averaging 8.8 t/ha. The Monsanto hybrid DCS 4014 had a fairly high yield of 7.6 t/ha. The minimum yield value in the studies was recorded in the hybrid DN Patriot (5.9 t/ha).

The results obtained suggest that the corn yield is largely determined by the growing conditions and genetic characteristics of the hybrid.

Thus, one of the reserves for increasing corn yields is the rapid introduction of hybrids with high heterosis and productivity potential, which will allow to increase grain production without unnecessary costs. Corn grain yields are largely determined by the morphological and biological properties of crop biotypes, weather conditions during the growing season, and agronomic practices. Increased yields, high drought resistance, good moisture retention, well-developed root system and stems are the advantages that distinguish corn hybrids in the experiment.

Sweet corn (*Zea mays saccharata*) is a valuable crop characterized by a high sugar content in its ker-

nels, which makes it indispensable for fresh consumption and canning. It is important in the food industry as a source of vitamins, minerals and antioxidants. This crop is widely grown due to its unpretentiousness to growing conditions and high profitability.

The yield of sugar corn depends on agronomic practices, including the right choice of hybrids, irrigation and nutrition systems. On average, the yield reaches 4–8 tons per hectare, and under favorable conditions - even more. It adapts well to different climatic zones, which allows it to be grown in many regions. In addition, sugar corn is an early ripening crop, which ensures a quick harvest. Its products are in constant demand on the market, especially in the summer and autumn. Due to its characteristics and nutritional value, sugar corn plays an important role in modern agriculture and nutrition.

We analyzed the yields of four hybrids of sugar corn (Fig. 4) and identified the most productive ones in Polissia.

Fig. 4. Sugar corn hybrids, 2024

To assess the productivity of sugar corn, a study was conducted on the yield of different hybrids. The main focus was on the impact of weather conditions and agronomic practices on the final result. Figure 5 shows the yield data, which demonstrates variations depending on agronomic practices and hybrid characteristics.

Fig. 5. Yields of sugar corn hybrids, 2022-2024

This allows us to determine the most effective hybrids for growing in the conditions of a particular farm. The presented results help to optimize the technology of growing sugar corn to achieve maximum productivity.

The maximum grain yield in all years of the study was formed by the Raquel F1 hybrid, averaging 4.8 t/ha. The hybrid Megaton F1 had a fairly high yield of 3.7 t/ha. The minimum yield value in the studies was recorded in the Dobrynya F1 hybrid (3.1 t/ha).

The quality characteristics of sugar corn hybrids play an important role in determining their economic value. The main characteristics include sugar content in the kernels, cob structure, plant alignment and product uniformity. Hybrids with a high sugar content are the most attractive for fresh consumption and processing, as they provide a sweet flavor and excellent palatability. Careful selection of hybrids with high quality indicators (crude protein, fat, fiber) is the key to successful sugar corn cultivation (Table 1).

Table 1

Hybrid	Quality indicators of sugar corn, %.		
	Raw Protein, %	Crude fat, %	Crude fiber, %.
Raquel F1	9,5	4,90	2,73
Dobrynya F1	8,8	4,41	2,46
Megaton F1	9,4	4,78	2,62
GSS 3071	9,1	4,52	2,59

Table 1 contains data on the main biochemical parameters of sugar corn hybrids, such as crude protein, fat and fiber content. The RAKEL F1 hybrid has the highest protein (9.5 %) and fat (4.90 %) content, which makes it promising for cultivation to increase nutritional value. The Dobrynya F1 hybrid has slightly lower protein (8.8 %) and fat (4.41 %), but retains good taste. Megaton F1 demonstrates similar indicators to RAKEL F1, which indicates its high quality. GSS 3071 is characterized by stable average values for both protein (9.1 %) and fiber (2.59 %).

Conclusions. The study of the productivity of grain corn and sugar corn hybrids in the Polissia and Forest-Steppe regions of Ukraine showed that the agrolimatic conditions of these regions significantly affect crop yields. It has been established that the choice of hybrid is the determining factor for obtaining a stable yield. Corn hybrids for grain in the Forest-Steppe showed higher productivity, while in Polissia the best

results were demonstrated by sugar corn hybrids. The maximum yield of corn for grain in all years of the study was formed by the Adeway hybrid, averaging 8.8 t/ha, while the sugar maize Raquel F1 yielded 4.8 t/ha. Favorable weather conditions and adherence to agro-technical recommendations can improve the quality and quantity of the crop. The results of the research can be used to optimize corn growing technologies in different regions of Ukraine, taking into account the characteristics of each hybrid.

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